

LEGAL NOTE

At the request of some co-authors, a white paper, which was authored by members of IAAT and independent researchers, has been taken offline without acknowledging any legal obligation.

IAAT has complied with this request as a courtesy and is allowing the first submitter to publish this notice.

John Ernst
Head of Legal Department

